

STUDY OF GALVANIC CORROSION OF MILD STEEL COATED WITH AZ91D MAGNESIUM ALLOY BY COMSOL MULTIPHYSICS

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Abstract

Pipeline corrosion is associated with a global economic loss of \$1.3 billion yearly, also it increases risk of spillage of flammable and toxic substances that can result in significant safety hazard. Pipeline corrosion was studied by analyzing galvanic corrosion between pipe steel and AZ91D magnesium alloy coating. It was found that, as the radius of the hollow and the total radius of the pipe decreased and as the magnesium alloy coating thickness increased, corrosion rate and current density decreased, and galvanic corrosion potential increased at the outer surface of the magnesium coating however the changes are not pronounced in intersection between steel and magnesium coating.

Introduction

Corrosion is the process of gradual deterioration of the materials by electrochemical or environmental factors. Corrosion is a challenging phenomenon in terms of performance and longevity of advanced technologies including electronics, medical implants and renewable energy systems. One of the most common types of corrosion is galvanic corrosion. Galvanic corrosion happens when two metals encounter each other in electrolyte, one metal can be considered as anode and the other metal can be considered as a cathode based on the potential of these two metals. In this case, electron moves from anode to cathode and anode gets corroded by being dissolved in the electrolyte. The rate of the galvanic corrosion can be calculated based on the equation-

$$I_g = (E_c - E_a)/(R_a + R_c + R_m + R_s) \quad [1]$$

Here, galvanic corrosion is determined by I_g , E_c is the equilibrium potential of cathode and E_a is the equilibrium potential of anode, R_a is the resistance for anode, R_c is the resistance for cathode, R_s is the solution resistance, R_m is the resistance from anode to cathode.[1]

In the galvanic corrosion process the metal which is less noble, works as a sacrificial anode, which protect the more noble metal that work as a cathode. Only when the anode gets completely dissolved into the electrolyte, cathode tends to rust. For example, Iron can rust only when zinc coating is totally corroded, in the event of iron coated with zinc immersed in an electrolyte solution. Galvanic corrosion has been studied by many researchers based on different parameters. Galvanic corrosion between galvanized steel and mild steel at different pH was studied by Vagge *et.al.*,[2] change of corrosion rate with electrolyte thickness between steel bolt and plate joint had been studied by Essali.M *et.al.*,[3] the presence of two microstructures in magnesium alloy was studied by Deshpande.KB,[4] galvanic corrosion between magnesium and aluminum was studied by Loic Lacroix *et.al.*,[5] Nicolas Murer *et.al.*[6] observed that due to the presence of insulator between aluminum alloy galvanic corrosion rate increased. Similar insulator edge effect was also observed in the galvanic corrosion study between magnesium alloy (AE44) and mild steel done by Dao Trinh *et.al.* and it was found that due to the presence of insulator galvanic corrosion rate increased.[7] In the galvanic corrosion study between rivets made of steel joint and aluminum plate, Y.Zhang *et.al.* observed that corrosion rate was maximum around the joint and corrosion rate was lowest at the edges.[8] One of the most convenient way to measure galvanic corrosion rate is using simulation procedure. In this research work galvanic corrosion between pipe steel and AZ91D magnesium alloy coating has been studied by a finite element analysis (FEA) mathematical model developed using COMSOL Multiphysics 4.2.

Materials and methods

Galvanic corrosion between pipe steel and AZ91D magnesium alloy coating immersed in 5 wt% aqueous NaCl solution which had a conductivity of 7.9500 S/m and height of the solution was 7.5 cm was studied by COMSOL Multiphysics. 10-inch pipeline of schedule 40 and 80 and 12- inch pipeline of schedule 40 and 80 and magnesium coating of 8 different thickness were used for the study.

Table 1. AZ91D Mg alloy has the percentage composition as following [9]

Aluminium	8.3-9.7
Copper	0.03 max
Magnesium	88.6-91.04
Iron (max)	0.005
Nickel (max)	0.002
Zinc	0.35-1.0
Manganese	0.15-0.5
Silicon	0.1 max
Other metallic	0.02

Table 2. The percentage chemical composition of mild steel is as following [10]

Carbon	0.16-0.18
Silicon	0.40 (max)
Manganese	0.70-0.90
Sulphur	0.040 (max)
Phosphorous	0.040 (max)
Iron	98.44-98.66s

For different values of radius of hollow radius, radius of outer radius of the pipeline and different values of the magnesium coating thickness simulated values of the variation in electrode potential and current density were obtained for the galvanic couple. Maximum values for the current densities and potential were considered for analyzing the corrosion behavior of the system.

Figure 1. Variation in the electrode potential with radius in the galvanic couple of stainless steel and magnesium coating a) 2D image, b) 3D image

Figure 2. Schematic diagram of steel pipeline with magnesium coating

The schematic diagram in Figure 2 is showing the pipeline image where R1 is representing the radius of the hollow, R2 is representing the outer radius and R3 is representing the total radius, that is the outer radius plus the radius of the magnesium coating.

Table 3. The following 32 experiments were performed for the pipelines of 10 inch and 12 inch having 40 and 80 schedule number respectively and for eight different magnesium coating thickness.

Test no	Nominal pipe size (inch)	Outer Diameter (inch)	Inner Diameter (inch)	Schedule number	Thickness of Mg coating (inch)	R1 (m)	R2 (m)	R3 (m)
1	10	10.75	10.02	40	0.0625	0.127254	0.136525	0.265367
2	10	10.75	10.02	40	0.125	0.127254	0.136525	0.266954
3	10	10.75	10.02	40	0.1875	0.127254	0.136525	0.268542
4	10	10.75	10.02	40	0.25	0.127254	0.136525	0.270129
5	10	10.75	10.02	40	0.3125	0.127254	0.136525	0.271717
6	10	10.75	10.02	40	0.375	0.127254	0.136525	0.273304
7	10	10.75	10.02	40	0.4375	0.127254	0.136525	0.274892
8	10	10.75	10.02	40	0.5	0.127254	0.136525	0.276479
9	10	10.75	9.562	80	0.0625	0.121437	0.136525	0.25955
10	10	10.75	9.562	80	0.125	0.121437	0.136525	0.261137
11	10	10.75	9.562	80	0.1875	0.121437	0.136525	0.262725
12	10	10.75	9.562	80	0.25	0.121437	0.136525	0.264312
13	10	10.75	9.562	80	0.3125	0.121437	0.136525	0.2659
14	10	10.75	9.562	80	0.375	0.121437	0.136525	0.267487
15	10	10.75	9.562	80	0.4375	0.121437	0.136525	0.269075
16	10	10.75	9.562	80	0.5	0.121437	0.136525	0.270662
17	12	12.75	11.938	40	0.0625	0.151613	0.161925	0.315125
18	12	12.75	11.938	40	0.125	0.151613	0.161925	0.316713
19	12	12.75	11.938	40	0.1875	0.151613	0.161925	0.3183
20	12	12.75	11.938	40	0.25	0.151613	0.161925	0.319888
21	12	12.75	11.938	40	0.3125	0.151613	0.161925	0.321475
22	12	12.75	11.938	40	0.375	0.151613	0.161925	0.323063
23	12	12.75	11.938	40	0.4375	0.151613	0.161925	0.32465
24	12	12.75	11.938	40	0.5	0.151613	0.161925	0.326238
25	12	12.75	11.374	80	0.0625	0.14445	0.161925	0.307962
26	12	12.75	11.374	80	0.125	0.14445	0.161925	0.30955
27	12	12.75	11.374	80	0.1875	0.14445	0.161925	0.311137
28	12	12.75	11.374	80	0.25	0.14445	0.161925	0.312725
29	12	12.75	11.374	80	0.3125	0.14445	0.161925	0.314312
30	12	12.75	11.374	80	0.375	0.14445	0.161925	0.3159
31	12	12.75	11.374	80	0.4375	0.14445	0.161925	0.317487
32	12	12.75	11.374	80	0.5	0.14445	0.161925	0.319075

Results and discussions

For 8 different magnesium coating thickness change of current density, electrochemical potential and corrosion rate were analyzed for pipeline of 10-inch length and pipeline of 12-inch length having schedule 40 and 80 respectively.

It was found that, as the total radius of the pipe and the magnesium alloy coating thickness increased and the hollow radius increased, current density decreased in the outer surface of the magnesium coating, however the changes are not pronounced at the at the intersection between steel and magnesium coating which can be seen in Figure 3

Figure 3. Current density a) at the intersection between steel and magnesium coating and current density b) at the outer surface of magnesium coating

Again since there is a linear relationship between current density and corrosion rate [11], it was observed that, as the total radius of the pipe and the magnesium alloy coating thickness increased and the hollow radius increased, corrosion rate decreased in the outer surface of the magnesium coating, however the changes are not pronounced at the intersection between steel and magnesium coating that is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Corrosion rate a) at the intersection between steel and magnesium coating and corrosion rate b) at the outer surface of magnesium coating

Since, due to the polarization effect with the increase of galvanic potential current density and corrosion rate decreases it was observed that, as the total radius of the pipe and the magnesium alloy coating thickness increased and the hollow radius decreased, galvanic potential increased in the outer surface of the magnesium coating, however the changes are not pronounced at the at the intersection between steel and magnesium coating that can be seen in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Galvanic potential a) at the intersection between steel and magnesium coating and b) galvanic potential at the outer surface of magnesium coating

Conclusion

Change of current density, corrosion rate and galvanic potential for the galvanic corrosion between pipe steel and AZ91D magnesium alloy coating have been analyzed in this research article by varying different hollow radius, outer radius and magnesium coating thickness for the pipeline of size 10 inch and 12 inch and schedule no. 40 and 80 respectively. It was found that with the increase of total pipeline radius and magnesium coating thickness and the hollow radius decreased, current density and corrosion rate increases and galvanic corrosion rate decreases in the outer surface of the magnesium coating. This information can be useful for predicting lifeline of pipeline which can be useful for safety and economic purpose.

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